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**MEMORANDUM SUBMITTED BY THE GHANA MUST KNOW
(GMK) MOVEMENT IN SUPPORT OF THE ANTI - LGBTQ++ BILL
BEFORE PARLIAMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF GHANA**

We the underlisted citizens of Ghana submit this memo in support of Parliament passing this Bill into law.

This petition is borne out of our individual and collective intractable conviction that gauges as repugnant such LGBTQ+++ human practices, some Ghanaians are demanding to be upheld. Homosexuality is seen as a choice and not a human right issue. This is epitomised in the 1992 Constitution of Ghana, per article 12(2) that stipulates:

*Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individuals contained in this Chapter **but subject to the respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for public interests.***

Referenced from the above Constitutional provision, we strongly believe that respect for rights, freedoms and interests of others remain paramount in this national discourse. Statistically, all religions recognized by the Ghanaian constitution, namely: Christianity, Islam and traditional religions abhor such practices. A CDD research outcome corroborates, pointing out that more than 90% of Ghanaians detest these lifestyles. It reasons to confirm that Ghanaians hate this menace, and will not like it to be discussed as a national issue at all.

It is an indisputable fact that the practice of homosexuality, including its and other emerging queer lifestyles has got the tendency to derail our cherish national traditions, culture, norms and faiths that have guided and bounded we Ghanaians together as a people and as one interwoven inseparable fraternity for the past eons of years in our existence as a race.

It is again an incontrovertible fact that the subtle creeping of the introduction of homosexuality and its complex and associated undertones into the fabric of Ghana SHALL not only breed moral turpitude, but also erode the dignity of natural order involving two consenting adults (man and woman) of which Ghana is not an exception.

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